

Comparative analysis of image super-resolution: A concurrent study of RGB and depth images

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Abstract—The introduction of deep learning has significantly advanced super-resolution techniques, allowing for the extraction of detailed textures and nuances vital for accurately analyzing visual information. The main contribution of our study is the development of the iDFD-SR dataset, an enhancement of the existing Indoor Depth from Defocus (iDFD) dataset [1], designed to evaluate super-resolution algorithms in the complex and varied indoor settings. Utilizing cutting-edge deep learning models such as EDSR (Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution Network), ESRGAN (Enhanced Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Networks), RDN (Residual Dense Network), LIIF (Local Implicit Image Function) and HAT (Hybrid Attention Transformer), we perform a thorough comparison across several datasets—All in Focus (AIF), Out of Focus (OOF), Raw Depth (DR), and Depth after In-Painting (DI)—to identify the strengths and challenges of each approach. Our findings demonstrate notable enhancements in image quality for both RGB and depth images. However, the research acknowledges limitations, notably its indoor setting focus and the extensive computational resources required. Future work aims to broaden the application of super-resolution techniques, increase computational efficiency, and enhance the accuracy of depth estimations.

Index Terms—Super resolution, Deep learning, Image quality, Performance analysis, Indoor environment

I. INTRODUCTION

Image super-resolution (SR) enhances the resolution of images, which is crucial for applications such as medical imaging and surveillance [2]. Traditional methods relied on interpolation techniques with limited success [3]. The advent of deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and generative adversarial networks (GANs), has revolutionized SR by learning intricate patterns and textures, leading to significant advancements [4]. This active research area in computer vision is especially relevant for RGB-D imaging, which requires both RGB and depth information for various applications [5]. Recent deep learning methods have substantially improved SR capabilities, enhancing the extraction of finer details and textures essential for accurate visual representation [6].

Image super-resolution is particularly relevant in the context of RGB-D imaging, where both RGB and depth information are crucial for a wide range of applications. With the introduction of deep learning methods, the capabilities in super-resolution have seen substantial improvements. These advancements facilitate the extraction of finer details and textures, which are imperative for the accurate representation and analysis of visual information. This study introduces the iDFD-SR dataset, enhancing the iDFD dataset to benchmark super-resolution methods, particularly in indoor environments characterized by diverse and complex scenes.

The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- 1) iDFD-SR Dataset Development: Enhances the Indoor Depth from Defocus (iDFD) dataset to focus on super-resolution in indoor environments, providing a critical benchmark for evaluating super-resolution algorithms in realistic settings.
- 2) Advanced Deep Learning Networks: Utilizes state-of-the-art deep learning networks such as EDSR, ESRGAN, RDN, LIIF and HAT, highlighting each model's role in advancing image quality improvement.
- 3) Comparative Analysis Across Datasets: Conducts thorough evaluations of these networks over different datasets, offering detailed insights into their effectiveness and limitations for super-resolution tasks.

II. RELATED WORK

A. RGB-D datasets

In images super-resolution tasks, RGB-D datasets are broadly categorized into synthetic datasets [7], [8], created through computer simulations, and real-scene datasets, consisting of images captured from natural settings. Depth images in real-scene datasets are typically obtained using either stereo correspondence [9], which estimates depth from images taken at different angles, or Time of Flight (ToF) cameras, which measure the time light takes to reflect back from

objects. ToF cameras excel in accurate depth measurement, as they directly calculate the travel time of light to and from objects. This method ensures precise depth data, essential for detailed image analysis. ToF cameras also perform reliably under different lighting conditions, unlike methods like stereo correspondence, which may falter in low light. Additionally, they require a simpler setup and provide consistent results across various scenes, making them a preferred choice for generating robust and reliable RGB-D datasets.

Table I presents a compilation of various RGB-D datasets that have been generated using ToF cameras. It can be seen from the table that the dataset we generated have high resolution. Additionally, we provide out-of-focus images within the dataset.

TABLE I
THE COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT RGB-D DATASETS USING TIME OF FLIGHT CAMERAS.

Dataset	Images	RGB resolution	Depth Resolution
NYU-Depth V2	1449	640×480	640×480
SUN RGBD	10335	Multi	Multi
RGB-D-D	4811	512×348(HR) 192×144(LR)	512×348(HR) 192×144(LR)
iDFD-SR	764	640×480(HR) 160×120(LR)	640×480(HR) 160×120(LR)

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Deep learning networks implemented in this study

a) *EDSR (Enhanced Deep Super-Resolution Network) [10]*: EDSR simplifies the traditional residual network by removing batch normalization layers. This leads to less memory usage and simpler computations, allowing it to handle larger feature maps and thus improve detail in image reconstruction. EDSR is made up of several residual blocks, aiding in better feature learning and image detail enhancement. EDSR is selected for its efficiency in enhancing high-resolution images, both crucial for RGB and depth images.

b) *ESRGAN (Enhanced Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Networks) [11]*: ESRGAN uses a generative adversarial network (GAN) framework with a novel perceptual loss function, focusing on improving the realism of super-resolved images. The introduction of Residual-in-Residual Dense Blocks (RRDB) without batch normalization enhances image quality and model stability. The model also includes a discriminator network, which helps in generating more natural-looking images. ESRGAN is adept at generating realistic textures, making it highly suitable for RGB images where texture fidelity is crucial. In depth images, ESRGAN can enhance edge and surface details.

c) *RDN (Residual Dense Network) [12]*: Combining residual and dense connections, RDN forms Residual Dense Blocks for efficient feature extraction. This network structure allows for detailed exploration of image data at different scales, leading to better detail recovery. RDN also employs a feature fusion strategy, which consolidates the learned

features for improved image reconstruction. RDN is effective for both RGB and depth images due to its dense feature extraction, which captures comprehensive image details. It enhances color and texture in RGB images and preserves important spatial details in depth images.

d) *LIIF (Local Implicit Image Function) [13]*: LIIF introduces an approach where an implicit neural representation is learned for image coordinates, allowing image generation at any resolution. This model encodes local features into a continuous space, enabling precise pixel-level predictions. This approach is fundamentally different from traditional discrete pixel prediction methods, offering more flexibility and potentially higher accuracy. For RGB images, its continuous representation allows for flexible resolution outputs with high fidelity. In depth images, LIIF’s precision in spatial representation can significantly enhance depth map resolution and accuracy.

e) *HAT (Hybrid Attention Transformer) [14]*: HAT is a novel approach designed for image restoration tasks such as image super-resolution and denoising. It combines channel attention and window-based self-attention to better utilize input information and activate more pixels for improved restoration. HAT introduces an overlapping cross-attention module to enhance interactions between neighboring window features and employs a same-task pre-training strategy to further exploit the model’s potential.

B. Dataset preparation

In this study, we generated a iDFD-SR dataset comprising 764 image pairs, each consisting of an All in Focus RGB image, an Out of Focus RGB image and its corresponding Raw Depth image, and Depth after In-Painting image. The dataset contains a variety of indoor scenes captured in 5 different environments: bedroom, living room, labs, kitchen, and museum. It is a refined version of our previously developed iDFD dataset. To prepare the dataset for our comparative analysis, we applied bilinear interpolation to downscale the images by a factor of four, creating low-resolution counterparts for each image pair. The All in Focus and Out of Focus RGB images in the dataset were captured using a DSLR camera, while the depth images were obtained using an Azure Kinect camera. The specifics of the image capture and processing methodologies are detailed in our prior publication on the iDFD dataset. The original resolution of the images in the dataset was 640×480 pixels. Following the downscaling process, the images were resized to a resolution of 160×120 pixels, which served as the basis for our analysis. This resolution adjustment was critical for assessing the performance of super-resolution techniques under study.

Fig. 1 shows some examples from the iDFD-SR dataset illustrating the variety of scenes and the quality of the depth maps as well as the RGB images.

Fig. 1. Sample from our iDFD-SR dataset. Each sample contains the All in Focus (AIF), Out of Focus (OOF), Raw Depth (DR), and Depth after In-Painting (DI) [1].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation Details

The experiments were trained on a Linux system with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU. Using the PyTorch framework, the Adam optimizer was set with an initial learning rate of 0.0001, halved at specific milestones to improve performance.

The training dataset was preprocessed with normalization, random cropping to 196x196 patches, and various augmentations to enrich the dataset. Over 300,000 iterations, we evaluated the model’s performance using Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), adjusting the learning rate dynamically for optimal convergence.

This succinct and efficient implementation strategy ensured our model’s ability to generate clear, high-quality super-resolved images.

B. Qualitative analysis

a) AIF (All in Focus): Figure 2 displays the results of different super-resolution methods on the AIF dataset. It also zooms in to show the details of the super-resolution results. From the outcomes, it is evident that the LIIF-EDSR and LIIF-RDN methods yield better results, particularly noticeable in the distinct separation of different color blocks without merging.

b) OOF (Out of Focus): Figure 3 presents the results of different super-resolution methods applied to an OOF dataset. In comparison to Figure 2, the same images and magnified areas were selected. The comparison demonstrates that the images from the OOF dataset exhibit better magnification results when out of focus.

The improved results seen in the OOF dataset may be attributed to the super-resolution algorithms’ proficiency in

Fig. 2. Comparative Visualization of Super-Resolution Techniques on the AIF dataset.

restoring details from images with a uniform blurring, as opposed to AIF images where the details are already sharp and the scope for improvement is less pronounced. Algorithms can often leverage the consistent patterns of blur present in OOF images to more effectively infer and restore lost details.

c) DR (Raw Depth): Figure 4 displays the outcomes of different super-resolution methods applied to the DR dataset. It also includes magnified views of specific details from the super-resolved results. It is observable that the super-resolved images are smoother in comparison to the ground truth. This effect arises as the algorithms typically interpolate between pixel values, which smoothens the image by minimizing the differences between adjacent pixels, thereby reducing prediction errors during enlargement.

d) DI (Depth after In-Painting): The figure demonstrates that the results of various super-resolution methods on the DI dataset are almost identical to the ground truth. This may be because inpainting itself is a generative process. When applied before the super-resolution process, it generates high-quality predictions of the missing details that can closely mimic the original image. As a result, when super-resolution is performed afterward, the pre-filled details by inpainting align closely with the actual high-resolution image, making the super-resolution output appear very similar to the ground truth.

C. Quantitative analysis

PSNR, and SSIM are metrics commonly used to evaluate the quality of images.

Fig. 3. Comparative Visualization of Super-Resolution Techniques on the OOF (Out of Focus) dataset.

Fig. 4. Comparative Visualization of Super-Resolution Techniques on the DR dataset.

Fig. 5. Comparative Visualization of Super-Resolution Techniques on the DI dataset.

PSNR is short for Peak signal-to-noise ratio, which is a widely recognized metric for objectively assessing the quality of image restoration. It can be described as shown in (1).

$$PSNR = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX_I^2}{MSE} \right) \quad (1)$$

where MSE is the mean squared error, and MAX_I is the maximum possible pixel value of the image.

SSIM [15] is a metric that evaluates the visual impact of three characteristics of an image: luminance, contrast, and structure, comparing the changes between a reconstructed image and the original one.

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (2)$$

Where: x and y are the two images being compared. μ_x and μ_y are the average pixel values (luminance) of images x and y , respectively. σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variance of images x and y , reflecting contrast. σ_{xy} is the covariance between x and y , indicating the tendency of corresponding pixels in x and y to vary together, which relates to structural information. c_1 and c_2 are small constants added to stabilize the division with weak denominators.

In the following analysis, we present a comprehensive comparison of various super-resolution methods applied to the iDFD-SR dataset, encompassing AIF, OOF, DR and DI images. Table II outlines the performance of each method, evaluated based on three critical metrics which have already

been introduced in the previous part. Two metrics serve as quantitative indicators of image quality, with PSNR focusing on the ratio of signal to noise, and SSIM on the perceived quality of the image. Higher PSNR and SSIM values indicate better performance.

TABLE II
THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT METHODS ON DIFFERENT DATASETS.

Methods	Dataset	PSNR	SSIM
EDSR	AIF	33.5647	0.9563
EDSR	OOF	38.7284	0.9732
EDSR	DR	29.833	0.9873
EDSR	DI	48.0495	0.9981
ESRGAN	AIF	34.1748	0.9601
ESRGAN	OOF	38.2302	0.9747
ESRGAN	DR	29.8465	0.9873
ESRGAN	DI	48.3984	0.9982
RDN	AIF	33.9818	0.9589
RDN	OOF	38.7821	0.9721
RDN	DR	29.4368	0.9865
RDN	DI	48.1458	0.9982
LIIF-EDSR	AIF	35.7853	0.9651
LIIF-EDSR	OOF	42.2585	0.9819
LIIF-EDSR	DR	34.747	0.9949
LIIF-EDSR	DI	52.7788	0.9986
LIIF-RDN	AIF	36.0063	0.9672
LIIF-RDN	OOF	42.5251	0.9826
LIIF-RDN	DR	35.1181	0.9932
LIIF-RDN	DI	52.8418	0.9986
HAT	AIF	36.7630	0.9710
HAT	OOF	42.8929	0.9843
HAT	DR	31.8021	0.9898
HAT	DI	49.8705	0.9984

Analysis on different Methods: From Table II we can see that LIIF-EDSR and LIIF-RDN show superior performance in the AIF and OOF datasets, with LIIF-EDSR achieving the highest PSNR and SSIM in the DI dataset, underscoring the benefits of integrating Local Implicit Image Function (LIIF) with existing methods for depth and focus-related enhancements.

The AIF and OOF datasets: The OOF dataset generally shows higher PSNR values for the same methods compared to AIF, indicating a better restoration of blurred images than bringing out details in already focused images. SSIM values also tend to be higher in OOF, suggesting that super-resolution methods are more effective at improving the perceptual quality of out-of-focus images.

The DR and DI datasets: Both datasets show high SSIM values. The DR dataset’s super-resolution outcomes tend to be smoother, as the techniques focus on interpolating pixel values, which can sometimes obscure fine details. Conversely, the DI dataset benefits from the in-painting process that fills missing details before super-resolution, resulting in outputs that more closely resemble the original high-resolution images.

The AIF and DR datasets: The AIF dataset demands the preservation and enhancement of fine details without creating artifacts. It is more challenging as indicated by the generally lower PSNR values compared to DR. The metrics indicate that

super-resolution techniques might find it easier to enhance depth images due to the smoothing effect that benefits depth estimation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the introduction of the iDFD-SR dataset marks a significant advancement in the field of super-resolution, especially for indoor scene analysis. We employed different deep learning networks such as EDSR, ESRGAN, RDN, LIIF and HAT across a variety of datasets, namely, All in Focus (AIF), Out of Focus (OOF), Raw Depth (DR), and Depth after In-Painting (DI). The study provides a thorough understanding of the unique advantages and challenges each method presents. The application of the Local Implicit Image Function (LIIF) alongside established super-resolution techniques has been demonstrated to substantially improve the resolution and quality of both RGB and depth images.

However, the study also acknowledges limitations, such as its primary focus on indoor environments and the high computational requirements needed for deep learning models, which could restrict the broader application and accessibility of these advancements.

Future research is encouraged to extend the application of these super-resolution methods into more varied environments, seek ways to optimize computational efficiency, and continue refining depth estimation accuracy. This aligns with the paper’s main objective: to perform a comparative analysis of image super-resolution techniques, focusing on both RGB and depth imagery.

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